

Supplementary Material

In this document we provide examples of the forms used for the Spring 2021 Stay-at-Home RevBayes Workshop (<https://revbayes.com/workshops/online2021.html>). All forms were created using Qualtrics to ensure accessibility in China. These forms include:

- Application form – The link to this form was posted on the course website and opened for four weeks. During that time, we recruited applications through advertising on social media and mailing lists.
- Confirmation form – This form was sent directly to all selected participants to confirm their attendance and acceptance of the workshop code of conduct. If a participant indicated that they could no longer attend the course, we would select someone from the waiting list.
- Feedback form – We solicited participant feedback after the conclusion of the workshop. This form asked the participants to evaluate the course delivery, learning materials, and the RevBayes software.
- Workshop code of conduct – Every workshop participant and instructor was required to accept the terms and policies outlined in the code of conduct.

Form and Survey Services

We chose to use Qualtrics for application submission and participant surveys because of its flexibility and accessibility. While Qualtrics is not a free service, many universities have institutional licenses and we were fortunate to be able to use this service through Iowa State University. We did investigate free options and found that the least restrictive free form service is Google Forms. However, because Google products are banned in China, this is not a viable option when including participants from that region. Another alternative is AirTable (<https://try.airtable.com/forms>), which does have a free version that may be suitable for future workshop application forms and surveys.

Application Form

Stay-at-Home RevBayes Workshop Spring 2021

A free virtual workshop on phylogenetic analysis using RevBayes

Website: <https://revbayes.com/workshops/online2021.html>

Thank you for your interest in the Spring 2021 Stay-at-Home RevBayes Workshop. This course will be held during April and May of 2021. Participants in the course will interact with the instructors and one another as they complete tutorials (detailed lessons on different RevBayes analyses with pre-recorded video guides). Additionally, we will hold 3 or more interactive sessions (the dates of these sessions are currently tentative and may be adjusted depending on the schedules of the workshop instructors and participants):

- Introductions and getting started – the first meeting in mid-April where participants and instructors will introduce themselves. The instructors will then assist the participants with installing required software and then provide a live demonstration of RevBayes and the Rev language.
- Tutorial sessions – participants will complete each tutorial on their own time and interactive sessions will be held to review the content and Q&A. The participants will also have access to a Slack group where they can discuss the tutorials or other course content with the instructors and their colleagues.
- Open lab sessions – the instructors will hold a series of discussion sessions to help participants synthesize what they have learned from the tutorials and apply the methods to their own data.
- 1-on-1 Meetings – at the end of the workshop, each participant will meet with one of the instructors to discuss and/or troubleshoot their analyses.

We are hoping to identify up to 20 participants for this online course. While we would like to accommodate everyone who applies, we realize that this is not possible because of time-zones and availability. Thus, we will only select applicants based in Asia-Pacific time zones: UTC+4 to UTC+12 (and UTC-10).

The first version of this workshop (<https://revbayes.com/workshops/online2020.html>) was held last summer and we selected participants from UTC-8 to UTC+3 time zones. If you are not selected or are not based in the target time zones, please keep an eye on the course website, as all of the materials will be made available online.

Applicant Details

Your name

Your email address

Your current institution

Your current city and country

Your current position/title

Are you a member of a group that is underrepresented in the fields of evolutionary biology and ecology? (optional)

Underrepresented groups are typically (though not limited to) racial/ethnic minorities, women, persons with disabilities, LGBTQI+ individuals.

No

Yes

→ (If yes) If you feel comfortable doing so, please indicate the underrepresented groups with which your identity aligns. (optional)

What are your pronouns?

(They/them/theirs, she/her/hers, he/him/his, ze/hir/hirs...please provide your pronouns in the text box below.)

In which time zone will you primarily be based during the workshop (mid-April to early June 2021)?

Refer to [this map](#) to find your time zone (if you live in an intermediate time zone that is not listed, please pick the time zone that is nearest to yours). Because of the logistical challenges of organizing a virtual workshop, we will only be selecting participants from a limited part of the globe. If you are not based in the target time zones, but would still like to indicate your interest in the workshop, please select "other".

UTC+4 (e.g., Muscat, Oman)

UTC+4:30 (e.g., Lahore, Pakistan)

...

UTC+13 or UTC-11 (e.g., Auckland, New Zealand or Alofi, Niue)

UTC+14 or UTC-10 (e.g., Kiritimati, Christmas Island or Papeete, Tahiti)

Other

Background and Research Interests

What are your primary research interests/questions?

What do you hope to achieve by attending this workshop?

Do you have empirical data you would like to analyze using RevBayes?

- No
- Maybe
- Yes

→ (If yes) Please describe the dataset you would like to analyze using the methods available in RevBayes.

Please provide some information about your previous experience with Bayesian phylogenetic inference.

For example: Have you attended other phylogenetics workshops or courses? Have you applied these methods in your research?

Please rate your level of expertise in the following categories:

	Unfamiliar	Somewhat familiar	Competent	Very Competent	Expert
Probability theory	<input type="radio"/>				
Bayesian statistics	<input type="radio"/>				
Markov chain Monte Carlo	<input type="radio"/>				
Phylogenetics theory	<input type="radio"/>				
Models of molecular evolution	<input type="radio"/>				
Macroevolutionary models & methods	<input type="radio"/>				

Please rate your level of expertise in the following software tools/platforms:

	Unfamiliar	Somewhat familiar	Competent	Very Competent	Expert
RevBayes	<input type="radio"/>				
BEAST	<input type="radio"/>				
MrBayes	<input type="radio"/>				
Unix/command line	<input type="radio"/>				
Statistical programming in R	<input type="radio"/>				

For this workshop, you will need to have access to a computer to complete the tutorials. What operating system will you be using while participating in this course?

Are there any potential factors that may limit your ability to participate in components of this workshop? Or other concerns you have about a virtual workshop format?

Confirmation Form

Stay-at-Home RevBayes Workshop Spring 2021

A free virtual workshop on phylogenetic analysis using RevBayes

You have been selected as an interactive participant in the virtual RevBayes workshop! We received over 100 applications from researchers all over the world. While we wish we could include everyone, we feel that we can only realistically manage 25 participants in the interactive parts of this course. The wide range of time zones can present a major challenge for online workshops. Thus, most of the interactions we will have in this course will be via Slack and interactive Zoom sessions at the beginning and end of the course. We also hope to provide some optional Q&A sessions via Zoom while you are working on the tutorials. And every participant will have the opportunity to schedule a 1-on-1 meeting with one of the instructors after the final session.

This form is for selected participants to confirm their attendance and commitment to engaging in the workshop. If you are unable to attend the interactive sessions or cannot participate in the community discussion (via Slack), please let us know so that we can select someone from our waiting list to take your place. The schedule of meeting times are provided in this form. All of the recordings and non-interactive materials developed for this virtual workshop will be available on the course page:

<https://revbayes.com/workshops/online2021.html>.

Applicant Details

Your name

Your email address

Will you be able to attend this virtual course by participating in the interactive sessions, joining the Slack team, and completing all tutorials?

Once you have confirmed your participation, we will send you the invitation to join the Slack team and additional information about preparing for the first session.

Yes

No

Please confirm that you can attend ONE of the introductory sessions

Because the instructors and selected participants reside in many different time zones, we have opted to hold two introductory sessions in the hopes that everyone can attend at least one. Please indicate which session you can attend. If you are unable to attend, or unsure, indicate what your constraints are in the text box question below.

Check your timezone based on UTC time here:

<https://www.worldtimebuddy.com/?pl=1&lid=100&h=100&hf=0>

	Yes, I will attend	No, I cannot attend	I am uncertain if I will be able to attend or not
Introductions & RevBayes Overview - April 21, 13:00-16:00 UTC	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Introductions & RevBayes Overview - April 22, 01:00-04:00 UTC	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please confirm that you can attend ONE of the final sessions

Please indicate which session you can attend. If you are unable to attend, or unsure, indicate what your constraints are in the text box question below.

Check your timezone based on UTC time here:

<https://www.worldtimebuddy.com/?pl=1&lid=100&h=100&hf=0>

	Yes, I will attend	No, I cannot attend	I am uncertain if I will be able to attend or not
Introductions & RevBayes Overview - April 21, 13:00-16:00 UTC	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Introductions & RevBayes Overview - April 22, 01:00-04:00 UTC	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If you answered that you cannot attend or are unsure of your ability to attend one of the sessions below, please inform us of your constraints. Please bear in mind that we received many applications for this workshop and, unfortunately, cannot include everyone. Thus, if you have several time conflicts, we may have to consider inviting someone from the waitlist in your place.

Code of Conduct

In order to participate in this online workshop, you must accept the terms outlined in our code of conduct. Please review our policies here:

https://revbayes.com/workshops/code_of_conduct/virtual_coc

Please indicate if you accept the Stay-at-Home RevBayes Spring 2021 Workshop **Code of Conduct**.

- I ACCEPT the terms and policies outlined in the code of conduct.
 - I DO NOT ACCEPT the terms and policies outlined in the code of conduct.
-

Feedback Form

Thank you for participating in the Spring 2021 RevBayes Stay-at-Home Workshop!

Because we hope to offer this workshop again in the future, we are seeking your feedback to understand ways we can improve the course delivery, material, or software.

Virtual Workshop Feedback

What were your primary goals for taking this course? Do you feel that you have achieved those goals?

What is your overall rating of the Stay-at-Home RevBayes Workshop?

1 2 3 4 5

🙄 poor ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ excellent 😊

What is your rating of the **organization** (timing, scheduling, and structure) of this virtual workshop?

	poor	fair	good	very good	excellent
Timing of Zoom meetings	○	○	○	○	○
Order of tutorials	○	○	○	○	○
Structure and organization of the Zoom meetings	○	○	○	○	○

Are there ways we could have improved the organization of this course, Zoom sessions, and the materials?

Please rate the quality of the **tutorial materials** and **course communication**.

	poor	fair	good	very good	excellent	not applicable
Phyloseminar lectures by Paul Lewis	<input type="radio"/>					
Tutorials (the text explanations, files, examples)	<input type="radio"/>					
Tutorial videos (provided on the RevBayes YouTube channel)	<input type="radio"/>					
The course Slack space	<input type="radio"/>					
Instructor communication and engagement	<input type="radio"/>					

Are there ways we could have improved the tutorial materials or course communication?

Please rate the quality of the **interactive sessions** (via Zoom).

	poor	fair	good	very good	excellent	not applicable
Introductory session	<input type="radio"/>					
Office hours	<input type="radio"/>					
Wrap-up session	<input type="radio"/>					
One-on-one instructor meetings	<input type="radio"/>					

Are there ways we could have improved the interactive Zoom sessions and 1-on-1 meetings?

Do you feel that you needed lectures on the background and theory of the methods you applied in the tutorials? Please explain your response.

(For this course we opted not to offer lectures, except for the Phyloseminar series by Paul Lewis.)

Are there methods/topics in Bayesian phylogenetics that you wish we covered in more detail in this course? If so, please provide your suggestions.

Was there any part of the course that you felt was especially challenging or frustrating?

Was there anything you especially liked or disliked about this course?

Are you likely to recommend this course to a colleague if it were offered again?

1 2 3 4 5

What are the reasons behind your recommendation above?

Why would or wouldn't you recommend the course?

Feedback on RevBayes Software

How likely are you to use RevBayes for your research?

1 2 3 4 5

Please elaborate on your selection above. If you are likely to use RevBayes for your research, how do you think it will benefit from our software? If you are unlikely to use it again, why?

Are you interested in becoming a RevBayes developer?

(If you are interested, please contact one of the instructors to learn more.)

- Yes!!
- No
- Maybe

What are the methods or features currently available in RevBayes that you are most excited about?

What methods or features that are currently NOT available in RevBayes would you most like to see in future versions of the software?

Please provide any additional feedback or information that you feel was not covered in this survey.

Are there any other thoughts that you'd like to express about the virtual workshop or RevBayes?

Virtual Workshop Code of Conduct

Policy on harassment and discrimination

Harassment of others by any participant (attendee or instructor) will not be tolerated. Unacceptable treatment of others includes (but is not limited to) unwanted verbal attention, intimidation, stalking, shaming, or bullying. Inappropriate behavior via any medium (e.g., direct message, chats, email, video conferencing) is a violation of this code of conduct. Discrimination or exclusion on the basis of gender or gender identity, sexual orientation, age, disability, physical appearance, race, religion, national origin, ethnicity, or similar will not be tolerated. Critiques of scientific work are appropriate and important, but all forms of communication must be free of offensive, discriminatory or disrespectful elements, including (but not limited to) words and images that are derogatory or demeaning to individuals or groups [1]. Inappropriate comments presented in a joking manner constitute unacceptable behavior. Retaliation for reporting inappropriate behavior is also unacceptable, as is reporting an incident in bad faith.

Workshop participants or instructors wishing to report a violation of this code of conduct by any member of this group can contact any of the instructors via direct message on Slack or email. Incidents of inappropriate and uncivil behavior are taken extremely seriously. Confidentiality will be maintained unless disclosure is legally required.

Workshop instructors will act as moderators in the Slack space and during interactive sessions. Instructors reserve the right to enforce this code of conduct in any manner deemed appropriate. Anyone violating the code of conduct may be: (a) asked to stop, (b) subjected to limits on or revocation of any means of active participation in the workshop (i.e., muted microphone, blocked video access, removed Slack access), (c) expelled from the workshop. Establishing and

enforcing this code of conduct is intended to prevent incidents of harassment, discrimination, and incivility, and to maintain a high quality of scientific discourse.

[1] Disagreements about science are normal and healthy parts of academic discourse. Civil and constructive criticism of someone's work for a perceived methodological flaw or a misinterpretation of results is appropriate. Demeaning a scientist for being sloppy, misleading or stupid and other ad hominem attacks are inappropriate.

[\[https://www.sciencemag.org/careers/2000/07/joy-criticism\]](https://www.sciencemag.org/careers/2000/07/joy-criticism)

Policy on liability

Instructors shall not be responsible for any defamatory, offensive, or illegal conduct of all participants, and shall not be held liable for or damage of any kind suffered by the participants at or in connection with the event. By registering for and attending the workshop, each participant acknowledges that they have read this Disclaimer, and expressly releases the instructors from any and all liability in connection with the workshop.

Procedures

Violations of the Code of Conduct are reportable to any of the instructors via direct message on Slack or email (see contact list on workshop website). In the case that a workshop attendee or instructor wishes to report inappropriate behavior of one of the workshop instructors, please consider contacting an instructor at a different institution.

Source

This Code of Conduct was adapted from policies established by Safe Evolution for the online and in-person Evolution Meeting activities sponsored by the Society of Systematic Biologists, the Society for the Study of Evolution, and the American Society of Naturalists.

[\[https://www.evolutionmeetings.org/safe-evolution.html\]](https://www.evolutionmeetings.org/safe-evolution.html)